

D1.3 Data Management Plan

Due date of submission: 30/06/2025

Actual submission date: 13/11/2025

Funded by
the European Union

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Table of contents.....	2
List of tables	4
Project information.....	5
Deliverable details	6
1 Description	7
2 Overview of Research Deliverables	7
2.1 Brief description of the described research output.....	7
2.1.1 2.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?.....	7
2.1.2 1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?.....	7
2.1.3 1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?.....	7
2.1.4 1.1.4 What is the type of dataset described?	7
2.1.5 What is its format?	7
2.1.6 What is its expected size?	8
2.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?.....	8
2.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?	8
2.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?	8
2.2 Publications.....	8
2.2.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?	8
2.2.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?	8
2.3 Software.....	8
2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?	8
3 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA	9
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata.....	9
3.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?.....	9
3.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?	9
3.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?	9
3.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?	9
3.1.5 Are the metadata searchable?	9
3.1.6 How are searchable metadata provided?.....	9
3.1.7 Are keywords provided in the metadata?	9
3.1.8 Are metadata harvestable?	10
3.2 Repository.....	10
3.2.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?	10
3.2.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?	10

3.2.3	Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?	10
3.2.4	Does the repository support versioning?	10
3.3	Data	11
3.3.1	How is the dataset / output shared?.....	11
3.3.2	Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?	11
3.3.3	Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?.....	11
3.3.4	Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends.....	11
3.3.5	Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for	11
3.4	Metadata	12
3.4.1	Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?...	12
3.4.2	Under which license will metadata be provided?.....	12
3.4.3	Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?.....	12
3.4.4	Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?	12
3.5	Making data and other outputs interoperable.	12
3.5.1	Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?	12
3.5.2	Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?	12
3.5.3	Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?	12
3.6	Increasing data and other outputs reuse	12
3.6.1	What internationally recognized license will you use for your dataset / output?	12
3.6.2	What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?.....	13
3.6.3	Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?	13
3.6.4	Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?.....	13
4	Allocation of resources.....	13
4.1.1	What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?	13
4.1.2	How will this cost be covered?.....	13
4.1.3	Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output	13
5	Data Security	13
5.1	What security measures are followed?	13
6	Ethical aspects	14
6.1	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output? 14	
7	Other	14
7.1	Do you make use of other procedures for data management?	14

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. An overview of the key research deliverables from work package 2-6 including expected data format and access for re-use 14

PROJECT INFORMATION

Project full title: Harmonised Life Cycle Assessment methods for sustainable and circular BIO based systems

Acronym: LCA4BIO

Call: HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01

Topic: HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-04 - Environmental sustainability and circularity criteria for industrial bio-based systems

Start date: 1st January 2024

Duration: 36 months

List of participants:

PARTNER Nº	PARTICIPANT ORGANIZATION	ACRONYM
1 (Coord.)	CONTACTICA SL	CTA
2	AALBORG UNIVERSITET	AAU
3	LUXEMBOURG INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	LIST
4	INSTITUT NATIONAL DES SCIENCES APPLIQUEES DE TOULOUSE	INSA TOULOUSE
5	NORGES TEKNISK-NATURVITENSKAPELIGE UNIVERSITET	NTNU
6	BIOECONOMY FOR CHANGE	B4C
7	BUSINESS E-INCUBATOR GO-UP	GOUP
8	FUNDACION CENTRO DE SERVICIOS Y PROMOCION FORESTAL Y DE SU INDUSTRIA DE CASTILLA Y LEON	CESEFOR
9	SONAE ARAUCO PORTUGAL SA	SONAE
10	ASOCIACION PARA LA CERTIFICACION ESPANOLA FORESTAL	PEFC ESPAÑA

DELIVERABLE DETAILS

Document Number:	D1.3
Document Title:	Data Management Plan versión 2
Dissemination level	PU – Public, fully open, SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
Period:	PR1
WP:	WP1
Task:	T1.4
Author:	AAU – Aalborg University Researchers: Agneta Ghose (orcid:0000-0003-1972-1433) Massimo Pizzol (orcid: 0000-0002-7462-2668)
Abstract:	<p>The Data Management Plan (DMP) describes the management of the life cycle of the data to be collected, processed and / or generated by the project.</p> <p>The aim is to make research data FAIR without compromising the property rights of the beneficiaries of the project. The DMP includes information such as: the procedures for handling research data during and after the end of the project, which type of will be collected, processed and / or generated, which methodology and standards will be applied; whether data will be shared or made open access and how data will be stored and preserved both during and after the end of the project.</p>

Version	Date	Description
Version 1	28/06/2024	First version of the DMP
Version 2	13/11/2025	Second version of the DMP

1 DESCRIPTION

The LCA4Bio project aims to address the development of suitable, precise and reliable assessment methodologies that enable the certification of Bio-based systems (BbS) and the proper comparison of environmental impacts of emerging bio-based technologies with current systems, considering up-scaling and future scenarios via Integrated Assessment Models (IAM) with manageable levels of uncertainty. Focus will be put on improving the assessment of circularity, dynamic carbon footprint, toxicity, air, soil and water quality.

This document provides the second version of data management plan (DMP) for the LCA4Bio project. This version of the data management plan provides a preliminary overview on the data expected to be generated from the LCA4Bio project. The structure of this document is based on the guidelines and template provided for data management in Horizon Europe. This document was generated by ARGOS which is an online tool, supported by OpenAire and EUDAT that address and recommend the use of FAIR and Open best practices. The DMP is a living document and will be continuously updated during the project. This is the first version of the data management plan.

All project participants who are involved with data collection, processing and storage must respect the procedures for data handling and the privacy strategy. All other project participants may consult this document to acquire an overview of the forms and of the usage of data in the project.

- DMP License License: CC-BY-4.0
- Access Rights: Public

2 OVERVIEW OF RESEARCH DELIVERABLES

2.1 Brief description of the described research output

2.1.1 2.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

2.1.2 1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

2.1.3 1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

2.1.4 1.1.4 What is the type of dataset described?

Derived or compiled

The LCA4Bio project aims to advance beyond the state-of-the-art LCA methodologies for the LCA of bio-based systems. Data from other projects and existing work done previously by the project partners might be re-used, at their discretion and permission.

2.1.5 What is its format?

The format of the expected data and research outputs is presently unknown. However, given that this project will build upon data and models developed in previous research some of the common data formats to be adopted are:

- Tabular data e.g. LCI inventory (.xlsx and .csv files)
- Models with software and code (.py, .pynb and html files)
- Documentation and tutorial (.pdf)

2.1.6 What is its expected size?

4 - 10 GB

2.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To improve a product
- To combine with other data

2.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The data will be provided by the LCA4Bio partners' research activities. Some partners may bring data to the project.

2.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Industry

The data will be useful for subsequent research carried on by the partners and any subsequent projects in the field.

2.2 Publications

2.2.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.2.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata.

3.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers (DOI)
- Researchers identifiers (ORCID)
- Organizations identifiers (ROR)
- Projects identifiers (CORDIS)

3.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

- DataCite Metadata Schema
- OpenAIRE Guidelines

3.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Administrative
- Structural

3.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.5 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.6 How are searchable metadata provided?

Metadata repository

3.1.7 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes. For generic repositories, the search keywords will be extracted from the metadata and provided as part of the descriptive metadata for the dataset. If there is a use of subject-specific repositories, the search keywords will follow the standard utilized by the given repository.

3.1.8 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes. Metadata harvest and indexation will be available depending on repositories' protocols. In Zenodo, this is harvested into the most common search engines for research data like OpenAIRE.

3.2 Repository

3.2.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

As no designated subject specific repositories relevant to the project have been identified so far, all partners have been advised to use Zenodo or their own institutional repository.

A community has been created in Zenodo to facilitate the findability of LCA4Bio datasets (<https://zenodo.org/communities/101135371>). Datasets deposited in Zenodo are provided with a DOI. When restricted data is stored on internal servers, partners are expected to include a note (essential metadata) on Zenodo regarding the existence of the dataset. Access will be decided by project partners, on a case-to-case basis. Partners will strive for describing a procedure for screening requests.

3.2.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Assigns PIDs
- Follows metadata standards
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Supports authentication and authorization of users

3.2.3 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes. All datasets deposited on Zenodo are assigned a DOI.

3.2.4 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.3 Data

3.3.1 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

LCA4Bio will strive to maximize open access of research data outputs. According to the project's scope, the research outputs are labelled following the expected method of usage (see Table 1):

- Open access; entries which are candidates for open research data.
- Limited access; parts of data shall be evaluated to see if it can be published as open research data, while sensitive data are expected not be made open. Reasons for limited access for data will be provided.

Irrespective of access, all metadata related to the data sets curated in this project will be made open access.

3.3.2 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.3.3 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

Yes

3.3.4 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

All data related to model and workflow development are being collected by project partners during the project, it will be shared and managed internally using Sharepoint.

During the project, information on specific access to the dataset (e.g. specific format for use in software) can be obtained from:

Anahí Fernández Casás (anahi.fernandez@contactica.es)

OR

Agneta Ghose (agneta@plan.aau.dk)

Data access after the project ends will be maintained on the metadata of the Zenodo repository.

3.3.5 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

The longevity of the Zenodo repository is approximately 20 years.

3.4 Metadata

3.4.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes, all meta data will be available on Zenodo to ensure findability and possibility to access data if deemed necessary (e.g. a review of models generated using this data).

3.4.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.4.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes. The name and contact details of data depositor and curator are provided in the metadata.

3.4.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes. Metadata is mandatory for all dataset(s) uploaded on Zenodo. All datasets (and metadata) published on Zenodo will be maintained for the lifetime of the repository (approximately 20 years).

3.5 Making data and other outputs interoperable.

3.5.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.5.2 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.5.3 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

All research outputs will be cross referenced. There is a provision to specify identifiers of related publications and datasets on the DataCite metadata schema provided by Zenodo.

3.6 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.6.1 What internationally recognized license will you use for your dataset / output?

Research outputs which are candidates for open research data will be certified as Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 or Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike 4.0

3.6.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Codebooks
- Data cleaning

3.6.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.6.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

4 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

4000 Euro

Funding for data curation, review meta data before publication

There is no indication of a need to budget for repository storage outside of the scope of what is accepted by repositories (in the case of this project; Zenodo) within their free limit quotas.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other, No additional cost is foreseen for long-term data preservation. All costs are included in the project budget.

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Agneta Ghose (orcid:0000-0003-1972-1433)

5 DATA SECURITY

5.1 What security measures are followed?

Each partner is required to follow the data security standards from their own institution, including guidelines for information security. This will also include local guidelines for backup and restore procedures, as well as for ensuring, e.g., the proper user management for confidentiality, integrity and accessibility of data. Where possible, partners will use certified solutions for storing data. Partners will transfer data using, either secure encryption transportation protocols, or by trusted encryption techniques, including proper transfer of encryption key(s) – as necessary.

In case not-aggregated data (or not anonymized data) are located in non-national servers, the permission request from participants may be needed. Nevertheless, data storage will be on the EU territory.

6 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

The project has received an ethical clearance in its Ethics Summary Report and it does not include any ethics deliverables. In terms of personal data, the Ethics Summary Report mentions the following: If personal Data will be collected via surveys, questionnaires, interviews, etc., and informed consent will be obtained for these activities. Data collected will be stored in EU-based servers and its use will comply with the GDPR Regulation 2016/679/EU.

7 OTHER

7.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Table 1. An overview of the key research deliverables from work package 2-6 including expected data format and access for re-use. *All open labelled deliverables will be uploaded on Zenodo and linked to the LCA4Bio Zenodo community. The DOI link will be provided after the review*

Work Package	Name of deliverable	Short description	Format	Access for re-use	Reason for Limited Access
WP2	D2.1 A harmonized methodology for dynamic and climate change impact calculation and pre-calculated dataset of dynamic inventories	Harmonization of existing dynamic carbon footprint methodologies building further on past projects (specifically CALIMERO & ALIGNED).	Report (.pdf); Demonstrator, pilot, prototype (.pynb, .py, .html)	Open / Limited	1) The dataset of dynamic inventories is based on databases that are connected to proprietary licenses (i.e. Ecoinvent v3). This restricts the use of the methodology and tools to practitioners who have access to Ecoinvent. 2) The original DyPLCA database (compiled datasets of dynamic inventories) is licensed and not freely available. For the updated DyPLCA database, developed in DyPLCA, it will be the same except for certain data points. In other words, this updated DyPLCA is not freely available and requires

					<p>additionally an ecoinvent license to operate.</p> <p>3) A system-level database version with all precalculated results (i.e. spreading system inventory over time), based on running the updated DyPLCA for all ecoinvent processes, will processes, will be made freely available if the user has already a license for ecoinvent 3.10 (see point 1)</p>
	D2.2 Set of circularity indicators for BbS and guidance document for sustainability assessment of circular bio-based strategies	Identify circular strategies that can be applied to BbS and define how in practice strategies for increased circularity that are usually considered for non-bio-based products as well as strategies for cascading use of resources, apply to BbS.	Report (.pdf)	Open	
	D2.3 A harmonized set of life cycle impact assessment methods, with additional temporal differentiation	A systematic review of indicators for the various impact categories in LCA (biodiversity, air, water and soil quality, water and land resources) relevant for BbS compared and harmonized into a set of impact methods.	Report (.pdf)	Open	
WP3	D 3.1 Review of pLCA approaches, conclusions and orientations for research	A systematic review of the relevant scientific literature to map: (1) how is "prospective" LCA defined (2) if a prospective version of the foreground and/or background	Report (.pdf)	Open	

	system is used, (3) whether and which external model has been used, (4) for which period, (5) covering which scenarios (6) for which (background) sectors, (7) if a tailored tool has been used or developed, etc.			
D3.2 Report with processes and strategies selected for upscaling inventories of low-TRL BbS	Generate LCI of up-scaled bio-based technologies for pLCA by harmonization of different techniques used for technology upscaling and tailor them to the case of bio-based low-TRL BbS technologies.	Report (.pdf)	Open	
D3.3 Dataset with upscaling factors and functions	The scale-up methodology will be built on a maximum of process unit typologies based on common engineering methods, providing benchmarks and guidelines.	data sets (.csv or .xlsx)	Open	
D3.4 Final version of IAMs coupled with background inventory database	Results of a tool that can directly couple process data of BbS in the foreground with IAMs data to streamline applications of prospective LCA of early-stage technologies, and quantify how direct and indirect resource usage (e.g., freshwater) & emissions to air, soil and water vary with a	Report (.pdf); Demonstrator, pilot, prototype (.pynb, .py, .html)	Open/ Limited	The background inventory used to couple with IAMs are connected to proprietary licenses (i.e. Ecoinvent v3). This restricts the use of the methodology and tools to practitioners who have access to Ecoinvent.

		range of future scenarios.			
WP4	D3.5 Guide on uncertainty	A practical framework for defining and accounting for uncertainty in prospective assessment of bio-based technologies based on existing classifications of uncertainty specifically the emerging bio-based technologies.	Report (.pdf)	Open	
	D4.1 Interim report of the results from WP4	Overview of the results developed in D4.2, D 4.3 and D 4.4	Report (.pdf)	Open	
	D4.2 Guidance document on substitution effect with indications for conducting comparative LCA studies between fossil/bio-based products (scientific paper/report)	Definition and analysis of methodologies for substitution effects of BbS.	Report (.pdf)	Open	
	D4.3 Guidelines on a method set for analyzing trade-offs with social and economic impacts	Methods to assess socio-economic trade-offs and synergies of BbS	Report (.pdf); Demonstrator, pilot, prototype (.pynb, .py, .html)	Open/Limited	This analysis builds on a previous tool (FLOREC-BASIC tool) access to which is under IP protection.
	D4.4 Guidance document on biomass constraints across sectors (scientific paper/report)	Accounting for competition for resources between BbS with energy, food, and feed sectors.	Report (.pdf)	Open	
WP5	D5.1 Two full examples to illustrate the implementation of pLCA at low-	Validation of pLCA methodologies in low-TRL bio-based systems	Report (.pdf); Demonstrator, pilot, prototype (.pynb, .py, .html)	Open/Limited	The inventory data collected from case studies to perform the LCA models might be liable to non – disclosure

WP6	TRL and high-TRL				agreements. Under such circumstances the access to inventory data will be restricted.
	D5.2 List of best available BbS and technologies and inventories of existing technologies	Identification and benchmarking of Best available bio-based systems and technologies	Report (.pdf)	Open	
	D5.3 Two guides to perform pLCA for low-TRL and LCA of high-TRL BbS	Final guidelines to perform LCA of BbS at High-TRL and Low-TRL technologies	Report (.pdf)	Open	
	D6.1 LCA methodological guidelines for the certification of High-TRL BbS	Co-creation process to define the LCA methodology for BbS systems between different stakeholders	Report (.pdf)	Open	
	D6.2 User-friendly tools to ensure applicability of improved methodologies	Creation of tools to ensure applicability	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype (.pynb, .py, .html)	Open	
	D6.3 Report on the applicability of tools after tests by potential users	Results on testing of tools by engaged stakeholders	Report (.pdf)	Open	
	D6.4 Conclusions of validation of certification scheme in PEFC-Spain	Inclusion and validation of LCA standards for BbS into existing certification scheme	Report (.pdf)	Open	